

A Critical Study of the Methods of Analysis of Lignin.

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The problem of estimating lignin in lignocelluloses has attracted much attention in recent years. The pioneers in the field are Cross, Bevan and Briggs (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3119) who regarded the maximum absorption of phloroglucinol under standard conditions as a new chemical "constant" of the lignocelluloses. All the direct methods for estimating lignin may be classified as acid hydrolysis and alkali extraction processes. Among the former may be mentioned those of Ost and Wilkening (*Chem. Zeit.*, 1910, 34, 461), Willstätter and Zechmeister (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2401) and Wenzl (*Papierfabr.*, 1922, 22, 101). Various workers such as Beckmann (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1921, 34, 285), Paschke (*Cellulosechemie*, 1922, III, 19), Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 357) have isolated lignin by extracting the substance with sodium carbonate or hydroxide solutions and precipitating the lignin by the addition of acid. Alkali extraction methods are as a class more tedious and give lower yields than acid hydrolysis methods and are therefore not suitable for quantitative analytical purposes. The recent method proposed by Schimidt (*Ber.*, 1923, 56B, 23) by treating the substance with an aqueous solution of chlorine dioxide is very unsatisfactory and is open to several objections which have been discussed in detail by Heuser (*Ber.*, 1923, 56B, 902). In the present paper a critical study is made of the determination of lignin by acid hydrolysis methods and its reaction with phloroglucinol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Finely powdered rice straw after extraction with ether for 3 to 4 hours was taken for all the experiments described below. The following results show that extraction of the straw with ether to remove the fat and resin is necessary before hydrolysing it with the acid. Higher results were uniformly obtained with the unextracted samples, the increase just accounting for the ether extract and a slight amount of residue was left after removing the lignin by chlorination which could not be further hydrolysed with sulphuric acid and which completely dissolved in ether.

TABLE I

Substance	% yield of lignin	% of the residue after the second chlorination	% solubility of the lignin in ether
Rice straw extracted with ether.	23.97	0.08	Nil
Do. before extraction with ether.	25.82	1.7 (soluble in ether)	1.6

Chlorination of Lignin.—In order to find out whether any cellulose was left unattacked after the acid hydrolysis, the lignin obtained by the different methods was chlorinated. After draining off the water under the pump the asbestos pad, containing the lignin, was chlorinated in a small beaker by passing a slow stream of washed chlorine for 15 minutes and stirring frequently with a pointed glass rod. Rapid reaction ensued and the substance became brown in colour. The chlorolignin was removed by digesting with 2 per cent. sodium sulphite solution and the residue after washing was chlorinated as above for another ten minutes for the complete removal of lignin. The percentage of residue left after the second chlorination of the lignins obtained by the different methods is given in Table III.

Phloroglucinol Absorption of Lignin.—This was determined by the method described in detail by Cross, Bevan and Briggs (*Chem. Zeit.*, 1907, 31, 725). The dried substance was treated at the room temperature for 18 hours with standard phloroglucinol solution and the excess of the phenol titrated with formaldehyde using as indicator the colour reaction of the phenol with lignocellulose, ordinary "news" printing paper being taken as test paper. The phloroglucinol filtrate of the straw was much more intensely coloured than in the case of lignin or the straw which was boiled with 12 per cent. hydrochloric acid. The filtrates of the latter were practically colourless. Pure cellulose does not show any absorption of the phenol. The phloroglucinol absorption values, which were determined, are tabulated below.

TABLE II

Substance	% of phloroglucinol absorbed calculated for 100 gms. of the dry straw	% of CHO in 100 gms. of lignin calculated from the phloroglucinol absorption value
1. Straw.	10.55	10.12
2. Straw which was boiled with 12% HCl for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour under reflux, washed and dried.	4.20	4.03
3. Straw freed from furfural-yielding bodies by repeated distillation with 12% HCl, washed and dried. (Krober's method.)	4.13	3.96
4. Lignin obtained by the sulphuric acid method.	4.05	3.89
5. Lignin obtained by the hydrochloric acid method (without boiling the acid).	4.32	4.30
6. Lignin obtained by the HCl method (after boiling the acid).	4.10	4.09
7. Lignin obtained by Wenzl's method ...	3.80	4.06
8. Residue after the second chlorination of lignin (first chlorination 15 minutes; 2nd chlorination 10 minutes).	Nil	Nil

Sulphuric Acid Method.—72% sulphuric acid is a very convenient reagent for hydrolysing cellulose. Complete hydrolysis is effected by digesting the substance with the acid for about 16 hours. There is considerable difficulty in filtering the lignin residues owing to the colloidal nature of the solution, even when a more dilute acid is used as recommended by Klason (*Cellulosechemie*, 1923, 4, 81). This can be overcome by diluting and boiling the solution. The following results show the effect of boiling on the yield of lignin :—

Time of boiling	% yield of lignin
Not boiled	26.46
15 minutes	24.21
30 minutes	24.01
60 minutes	23.97
120 minutes	23.98

It will be noted that the action is complete after half an hour and that no further loss takes place on continued boiling. In view of the above results the following procedure was adopted for the determination of lignin by this method. One gram of the air-dried material after extraction with ether was treated with 15 c.c. of 72% sulphuric acid in a well stoppered bottle and the mass intimately stirred with a glass rod. After hydrolysis at room temperature for 20 hours the acid was diluted to a concentration of 3% and the solution boiled under a reflux condenser for one hour. The lignin was then filtered through asbestos, thoroughly washed, dried at 105°,

weighed and ignited, and the percentage of ash-free lignin was calculated from the difference. The substance thus isolated is an amorphous dark powder insoluble in water and readily soluble in alkalis and ammonia.

Hydrochloric Acid Method.—Whereas ordinary concentrated hydrochloric acid (37% HCl) decomposes and gelatinises cellulose after about a day's action, a more concentrated acid (41-42% HCl) dissolves cellulose completely within a short time. The undissolved residue is lignin. The filtrate is slightly dark coloured, and a black precipitate is formed on diluting with water and boiling. When this precipitate is chlorinated for 7 or 8 minutes it becomes grey coloured and completely dissolves in a 2 per cent. solution of sodium sulphite giving the brilliant magenta colour produced by chlorolignin. The precipitate is therefore lignin which had passed with the filtrate in a colloidal state. The determination of lignin by this method was therefore done as follows:—One gram of the substance was treated with 20 c.c. of 42% hydrochloric acid for 24 hours at the room temperature. The solution was then diluted to a concentration of 12 per cent., boiled for 30 minutes under a reflux condenser, filtered through asbestos and the lignin estimated as usual. By prolonging the time of exposure of the straw to the acid for two or three days, higher yields were obtained probably due to the formation of lignin hydrochloride.

Wenzl's Method.—The reagent was prepared by gradually adding 25 gms. of phosphorus pentoxide to 100 gms. of fuming hydrochloric acid (d 1.19) while cooling with ice. The filtrate obtained on digesting the substance with this reagent contained some lignin in a colloidal form. One gram of the substance was therefore digested with 20 c.c. of this reagent for 24 hours, the solution diluted to 80 c.c. with water, boiled for 30 minutes and the lignin estimated. The following table gives the yields

and nature of the lignins obtained by the different methods:—

TABLE III

Method	% of lignin in the dry straw	Residue left after the removal of lignin by chlorination	% of furfuraldehyde in the hydrochloric acid distillate of the lignin
Sulphuric acid method ...	23.97	0.08	Trace
Hydrochloric acid method ...	23.10	0.15	Do
Wenzl's method ...	21.54	0.24	Do

Discussion of Results and Conclusion.

Cross and Bevan state that the phloroglucinol absorption value is characteristic of lignocelluloses "proportional to the degree of lignification of the substance and independent of the furfural-yielding constituents." It is, however, found that the absorption of the phloroglucinol by the straw is about $2\frac{1}{2}$ times as great as that of the lignin isolated from it. This large difference may be due to (a) decomposition of the lignin present in the straw during the process of isolation, or (b) absorption of the phenol by other groups present in the lignocellulose in addition to that of lignin or both. As lignin is highly resistant to acids it is not likely that any decomposition could have occurred in isolating it by acid hydrolysis methods. Any such loss is a negligible factor. This is seen from the fact that straw, which was washed and dried after boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid just for 30 minutes, shows almost the same absorption of phloroglucinol as the lignin isolated by digesting the substance for 24 hours with 42% HCl and diluting and boiling the solution for half an hour. If

there be any decomposition of the lignin a considerable difference between the two values might be expected. The second cause is therefore more important and it is shown that the increase in the absorption of phloroglucinol is almost entirely due to the presence of furfural-yielding bodies in the lignocellulose. Thus straw, from which furfural-yielding constituents are removed by distillation with dilute hydrochloric acid, shows practically the same absorption of the phenol as the lignin (see Table II).

The product of the reaction between lignin and phloroglucinol is the formation of lignin phloroglucide due to the presence of the aldehyde group in the lignin molecule. Beckmann and Ziesche (*loc. cit.*; also *Biochem. Z.*, 1921, 121, 293) give the formula $C_{39}H_{48}O_{14}CHO$ for lignin isolated from straw while according to Paschke, (*loc. cit.*) it has the formula $C_{38}H_{44}O_{14}CHO$. The percentage of CHO group in lignin calculated from the above formula is 3.78. The results given in Table II show that the figure for lignin calculated from the phloroglucinol value is 3.9 which closely agrees with the theoretical value. Lignin prepared from a different sample of straw gave the same phloroglucinol value as above, though the absorption of the phenol by the two samples of straw in their "natural" state showed considerable difference.

The reaction between phloroglucinol and lignocellulose is therefore in two directions, *viz.*, (1) the combination of the lignin group with the phenol and (2) the absorption of the phenol by the furfural-yielding groups in the substance, the first reaction producing a colourless compound and the second forming a coloured derivative.

The sulphuric acid method gives the maximum yield of lignin. No residue is left after the second chlorination and the substance is practically free from pentosans.

This method is the most convenient and is free from the drawbacks which accompany the other processes. In the hydrochloric acid method it is necessary to dilute and boil the solution after digesting the lignocellulose with acid in order to avoid the loss of lignin in a colloidal state. A slightly lower yield is obtained but the method may be considered satisfactory. Wenzl's method is not suitable for the quantitative determination of lignin as the reagent attacks the lignin molecule. The yield of lignin and the phloroglucinol value are much lower than the corresponding figures obtained by the other two methods. For isolating and estimating lignin the sulphuric acid method is therefore recommended.

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Fig. I